

HIGH VELOCITY IMPACT AND PENETRATION OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The static punch curve was used as a basis for the calculation of the energy required for penetration of composite laminates under impact conditions. The applicability of the static punch-through energy to predict dynamic penetration was examined for a range of thickness of the composite laminate specimens. The overall damage pattern in the dynamic case was similar to that of the static case. The residual velocities predicted using static punch-through energy overpredict the experimental values for thick laminates, but provide an easy and inexpensive upper bound approximation.

Keywords: graphite/epoxy laminate, dynamic impact, penetration, punch curve, shear plug

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composite laminates have become increasingly popular for use in structural applications, and they are also being considered for use in applications where the resistance against penetration under high speed impact is critical. Thus, it is important to have an understanding of the process of penetration of these laminates by a projectile under high velocity impact conditions. There has been much interest in the damage process of composite laminates under low velocity impact [1-4], but relatively little work has been done in the understanding of penetration of these laminates. A few experimental studies catalogue the residual velocities of various laminates under a range of striking velocities [5,8], but very few analytical models exist that describe the process of penetration of composite laminates. Zhu, et al [6] describe an analytical model for Kevlar-29/polyester laminates penetrated by a conical faced projectile. Lee and Sun [7] proposed a model based on the static punch curve to characterize the penetration process of graphite-epoxy laminates. This model was then used to predict the ballistic limit of laminates and compared with results from dynamic impact tests [8].

In this study, the static punch curves for various laminate specimens are first obtained from static punch experiments. The energy for penetration of the specimens under static conditions is then calculated. This static penetration energy (calculated for the penetrator used in the dynamic tests) is then used as an approximation for the energy lost from the projectile during penetration under dynamic impact conditions. The residual velocities predicted using the static penetration energy is thus an easy and inexpensive approximation of the experimental residual velocities that are

obtained after dynamic penetration. The accuracy of this approximation for a range of thickness of the composite laminate specimens is examined in this paper.

Graphite-epoxy (Hercules AS4-3501/6) laminates of 30.5 cm by 30.5 cm were fabricated from which specimens 9 cm by 9 cm were cut to be used for static and dynamic tests. A quasi-isotropic layup of with the sequence of $[(0/90/45/-45)_s]_n$ (where $n = 2,4,6,8$) was chosen for the sake of simplifying the damage mechanisms and for ease of modeling. Static punch through and dynamic penetration tests were performed on specimens 6.1 mm and 8.1 mm thick (corresponding to $n = 6$ and 8). The static punch curve and dynamic data for the two thinner laminate specimens, 2 mm and 4.1 mm thick (corresponding to $n = 2$ and 4) were taken from Lee and Sun [7,8].

2. STATIC PUNCH TEST

2.1 Experimental Setup

Static tests were performed for various specimens to obtain force-displacement curves during punch-through of the laminate. The static tests were performed on a 55 kip MTS universal testing machine linked with a computer using a data acquisition system. The blunt ended cylindrical penetrator 14.6 mm in diameter was made of hardened tool steel. The specimen was rigidly mounted and clamped between two steel plates 12.7 mm thick as shown in Figure 1 with circular openings of 43.8 mm diameter at the center to allow for penetration of the specimen. The loading was done at a steady stroke rate of 0.125 mm/s using a ramp signal.

Figure 1: The circular test fixture used for both static punch and dynamic impact tests.

The circular span area of the specimen was 43.82 mm which corresponds to a specimen span to penetrator diameter ratio of 3. The ratio of the thickness to the specimen span ratio was 0.139 and 0.186 for the thicker laminates in this experimental study and was 0.046 and 0.092 for the thinner laminates of [7,8].

2.2 Test results

The typical damage pattern for all the laminate types showed that a cylindrical plug of the same diameter as the penetrator was formed and pushed out of the specimen. The circular surfaces of the plug and that of the hole in the specimen were reasonably smooth indicating that this plug was formed due to shear. There was some amount of fiber breakage at the rear end of the specimen, for example, in about 3 or 4 plies in the 6.1 mm specimen. Di-iodobutane enhanced X-radiography on the specimens showed that delamination was present from the shear plug boundary until the clamped edge boundary for all types of laminates.

The typical force-displacement curves for the four different types of specimens are shown in Figure 2. The force-displacement curves show multiple peaks corresponding to the initiations of

different damage mechanisms such as matrix cracking, delamination, plug formation and pushout. Lee and Sun [7] did a series of punch tests on the thin laminates where the tests were stopped at various key points of the punch curve and the damage pattern was examined in detail. A finite element analysis using the commercial code MARC was also performed to simulate the punching process.

Figure 2: The static punch-through curves for the four different types of laminates.

At the point just after the first peak, there was no visible damage on the surface, delaminations that extended until the clamped periphery of the specimen and matrix cracks were found. A stress analysis using the maximum principal stress criterion predicted the location as well as the orientation of the matrix cracks. However, the matrix cracks were found to be formed before the first peak in the load displacement curve was reached and did not affect the transverse stiffness of the specimen. The first peak in each of the curves corresponds to the onset of delaminations which are induced in the double-ply layers by matrix cracks. The delaminations reduce the transverse shear stress that can be carried by the laminate, and the apparent transverse stiffness of the specimens decreases leading to a drop in load after the first peak. The last peak in each of the curves represents the formation of a shear plug of the same diameter as the penetrator. This shear plug is then pushed out under a monotonically decreasing load until the load levels off at a constant value.

3. DYNAMIC TESTS

3.1 Experimental Setup

The impact tests were performed with a pneumatic gun equipped with a self sealing pop action valve and pressurized up to 1.4 MPa using compressed gas. The projectiles 14.6 mm in diameter and 24 mm in length were made of hardened tool steel. These were propelled to incident velocities from 20 m/s up to 150 m/s before impacting normally with specimens mounted in their path. The incident velocities were measured using a set of photo-sensors the output of which was input to a timer. The residual velocities were measured using an electronic circuit triggered by the breakage of thin brittle glass plates mounted in the path of the projectile after penetration. The output from the circuit was captured using a digitizer and an oscilloscope to obtain the time interval between the breaking to the two brittle plates, from which the velocity can be estimated. A correction was made for the measured residual velocity values to obtain actual residual velocities. This correction was based on a calibration curve shown in Figure 3 which shows the velocities measured by the glass plate measurement system versus the corresponding actual velocities measured using the photo-sensors. The specimen and clamping fixture size was kept the same as in the static tests to allow for comparison of penetration energies without any further scaling.

Figure 3: Calibration curve of the glass plate system velocities against the photo-sensor velocities.

3.2 Test results

The experimentally observed residual velocities (V_{re}) are tabulated for various incident velocities in Figures 4 to 7, which correspond to laminate specimens 2 mm, 4.1 mm, 6.1 mm and 8.1 mm thick, respectively. During dynamic impact, the projectile may rebound from the target specimen, partially penetrate and remain inserted in the specimen, or completely penetrate the specimen. The cases in which complete penetration did not occur are represented in Figures 4 to 7 with zero residual velocity values at the corresponding striking velocities. The experimental ballistic limit velocity values can be obtained from these data. The typical damage pattern was similar to that in the static case and showed the formation and pushout of a plug along with some amount of fiber breakage on the rear side of the specimen. The front part of the hole where the plug formed had relatively smooth edges, but some plies at the rear end of the plug remained attached to the laminate along part of its circular periphery which gave the appearance of a partially open lid to the hole.

Figure 4: Plot of residual velocities versus striking velocities for the 2 mm thick laminates.

Figure 5: Plot of residual velocities versus striking velocities for the 4.1 mm thick laminates.

Figure 6: Plot of residual velocities versus striking velocities for the 6.1 mm thick laminates.

Figure 7: Plot of residual velocities versus striking velocities for the 8.1 mm thick laminates.

4. PREDICTION OF RESIDUAL VELOCITY

4.1. Finite Element Simulation

Lee and Sun [7] simulated the quasi-static punch-through of a clamped circular laminate specimen using the commercial finite element code MARC. This axisymmetric analysis used four noded elements to model the laminate and rigid surfaces to model the penetrator and clamps. The clamped boundary used in the experiments was modeled with insert boundary conditions using six noded semi-infinite axisymmetric elements which enforce zero displacement at infinite radius. The laminates are quasi-isotropic. The effective modulus scheme of [9] was used to obtain the elastic constants for the repeating sublaminates of $[0/90/45/-45]_s$. The CONTACT feature of MARC was used to simulate the displacement of the penetrator at a constant rate without overlapping the specimen model. The large displacement and update Lagrangean schemes were used to capture the nonlinear effects during the transverse displacement of the penetrator and laminate. Delamination in the specimen was modeled as a degradation in the apparent transverse shear modulus of the laminate. The degraded transverse shear modulus values were calculated semi-empirically for exact reproduction of the experimental static force-displacement curves. The load (or corresponding displacement) values at the first and last peaks of the load-displacement curves are the inputs needed from experimental punch curves. The plug formation after the last peak in the load-displacement curve was modeled using an array of double nodes, gap elements and a rezoning technique in MARC. The strain energy release rate calculated using the crack closure integral scheme [10] increased monotonically with the crack length in the plug. This showed that the plug formation was an unstable and instantaneous process once it is initiated at the last peak in the load displacement curve.

If the damage pattern and sequence during dynamic penetration is similar to that in the quasi-static punch tests, the load-displacement curve predicted using the above quasi-static model may be used to predict the force-displacement response during dynamic penetration. The simulation of the dynamic penetration can be performed as described in [8]. The implicit time integration method and a lumped mass scheme were used for the dynamic simulation. A point mass was assigned to the rigid surface corresponding to the projectile which was then impacted with the laminate model at a specified incident velocity. A slight structural damping was added to the elements in the model to stabilize the numerical response. The displacements at the peaks of the static curve were used to activate the degraded shear modulus and to end the analysis at shear plug formation. The load-displacement curve during shear plug pushout and passage of the projectile through the plug hole in the specimen can be approximated by a constant friction force. Using this dynamic finite element model, residual velocities were calculated at various striking velocities of the projectile. These residual velocities (V_{rfem}) are plotted against corresponding striking velocities in Figure 4 for the 2 mm thick laminates and in Figure 5 for the 4.1 mm thick laminates. We note that these residual velocities which take into account the dynamic effect provide good approximations of the experimental values.

4.2 Static Penetration Energy Model

An estimate of the energy required for penetration under quasi-static conditions can be obtained from integrating the area under the static force-displacement curve and adding the energy required for the pushout of the plug. As a first approximation, the force at which the plug is pushed out can be assumed to reach a constant value given by the terminal value in the force-displacement

curve. Thus, the energy required for penetration under quasi-static conditions is given by Equation 1,

$$E_s = E_{sc} + F_s (h+l-d), \quad (1)$$

where E_s denotes the total energy required for penetration under quasi-static conditions, E_{sc} is the energy obtained by integrating the area under the force-displacement curve, F_s is the steady friction force at which the shear plug is pushed out, h is the thickness of the specimen, l is the length of the projectile and d is the final displacement value of the static punch curve. A residual velocity can be calculated for each of the impact tests under various incident velocities assuming that the penetration process is essentially similar to the quasi-static case. The deflection of the specimen itself is taken into account in the static force-displacement curve if the dynamic effect during impact penetration is neglected. The 'predicted' residual kinetic energy of the projectile can be obtained by subtracting the quasi-static penetration energy from the incident kinetic energy of the projectile. Thus, the predicted residual velocity is given by Equation 2,

$$V_{rs} = \frac{2}{m} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} m V_s^2 - E_s}, \quad (2)$$

where V_{RS} is the predicted residual velocity, m is the mass of the projectile, V_s is the striking velocity and E_s is the static penetration energy given by Equation 1. The ballistic limit velocity, i.e., the velocity at which penetration will occur with zero residual velocity can be predicted for each of the laminates using Equation 3 as

$$V_{BS} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} E_s}. \quad (3)$$

The predicted residual velocities and ballistic limit velocities can be compared to the residual velocities experimentally obtained in the dynamic penetration tests. The predicted residual velocities are shown with the corresponding striking velocities in Figures 4 to 7 for the different types of specimens. The average value of the static penetration energy from a number of static punch tests for each type of laminate was used to calculate the predicted residual velocities. For the two thinner laminates represented by Figures 4 and 5, the predicted residual velocities are close enough to the experimental values for most practical purposes. However, the difference between the two values increases for the thicker laminates as can be seen from Figures 6 and 7.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

It can be noted from Figures 4 to 7 that the predicted residual velocities almost always over predict the experimentally obtained residual velocities. In other words, the energy absorbed from the projectile during dynamic penetration is almost always greater than that predicted by the static penetration curve. This difference is minimal for the thin laminates, but becomes significant for the thicker laminates of this study. This difference may be due to the fact that the dynamic effect of impact penetration is not considered in the model based on the static penetration energy. The variation in the predicted and measured residual velocities in some of the dynamic test data may be caused by slight obliquity of contact between the projectile and target specimens though care was taken during the testing to ensure normal contact and penetration. The overall damage pattern in the dynamic case was similar to that in the static punch tests. However, in some of the dynamic penetration tests for the thicker laminates, more plies at the rear end of the specimen

were formed into the lid-like structure rather than into the shear plug when compared to typical damage patterns in the static punch tests.

The predictions of the residual velocities are close to the experimentally measured values for the thin laminates and provide reasonably close estimates for the thicker laminates in this study. In all cases, the predicted residual velocities provided an upper bound to the experimental values. The residual velocities based on this simple model are easy to estimate and do not require any dynamic tests for their prediction. They are also a lot less expensive and tedious to calculate than those using the finite element simulation described earlier. The ballistic limit velocities can also be predicted reasonably accurately using this simple static penetration energy model. A static punch curve can thus provide a reasonably close estimate of the residual velocities during dynamic penetration. The predicted residual velocities from this model can be improved for thick laminates by including a correction for the energy consumed due to the dynamic effects and due to the slight changes in damage pattern during the dynamic penetration process.

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